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INFLUENCE OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF JUVENILE PERSONS ON THE ORIGIN OF CRIMINALITY AMONG THEM AND ITS THEORETICAL-PEDAGOGICAL ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the aspects of some characteristics in the physiology and psychology of young people who are reaching adulthood, that is, in the period of adolescence, which cause a tendency to crime. Proposals and recommendations related to this field of criminology are given. Together with this. Specific suggestions and recommendations have been given so that criminological characteristics and characters do not take root among young people.

Introduction: Juvenile criminological security as a scientific problem can be considered from two aspects: object and target. The object aspect involves considering the security incident from the point of view or perspective limited to the parameters of the object, that is, the minor himself and his environment. The objective aspect includes consideration of this phenomenon from the point of view of ensuring the goals of management influence on this object. Identifying, describing and explaining its situation as one of the main elements of the system of ensuring protection of minors from criminal threats. includes At the same time, the object itself, that is, mainly small, acts as a subject of this system at the same time, but its actions are also aimed at achieving the indicated result, that is, itself protects itself. A minor as an object of security against crime is considered in relation to his immediate environment, which depends on the level of protection against criminal threats or the level of reliability. At the same time, the higher the reliability of external protection, the more secure the minor feels.

Main part: Let us turn to the first aspect of the category of criminological security of the minor, under which we define the object of control or protective influence in the security system. People are such objects. Depending on the functional capabilities and goals of the protective effect, the object is considered classified: in it we distinguish between direct and indirect protection objects. The direct object is a minor who is subject to security measures. The mediating object is the people around the minor, on whose behavior the minor's criminological safety depends to different degrees: family members, peers (members of formal and informal groups), teachers, etc. such a theoretical concept as a part of oriented reality is actually quite traditional and general in nature. The conditionality of such a structure of the object is that the protective effect is directly on the minor, as well as on his

surroundings, which have different characteristics (criminogenic, anticriminogenic) and the degree of influence on him. can be equally applied to other persons. Of course, one cannot be limited to the general characteristics of the object, because it limits the knowledge about the object, which makes the control effect on it meaningless. Based on the methodological rules, the subject of knowledge is "an object in the broad sense, a visual image or any entity that is limited and visible in itself due to an internal semantic unity." It is important to know the internal and external relations of the object or its characteristics and relations.

Internal to relationships, knowledge subject as properties appeal who does Of course , we are this on the ground basically adult did not of the person personal features mean we hold. So protection of activity object as defined adult did not person" will and aspirations have was actor as , own thoughts, views, opinions representative as , da vo and to rights , mood and to grades have was creature is studied as " another human persons with together. Adult did not of the person o 'study on the subject external connections important sit down holds because they are his views, opinions, claims, moods and in grades important, often solution doer role plays, therefore for of the person spiritual and legal in its stability correct conscious (to the law subordinate) behavior, this is basically, criminal from the threat protection to do determines. But this of the object only one, positive side as will be seen. That's it with together, of the individual personal characteristics , as you know , each kind of , that's it including opposite - opposite to the feature have or to be possible: altruism and selfishness, determination and honesty, honesty and dishonesty and others. As you know, there are many personal virtues , especially in adulthood of those who did not psychological properties, increase going dynamism with is described. O'z in turn , behavior dynamism many p in terms of each how social individual with organic dependent was of the environment effect with dependent. That's why for too person features pole criteria (criminogenic and anticriminogen) on separate known level conditional it seems.

In jurisprudence the person is also a value opposite in the aspect , that is," criminal as a person considered.Criminology in science of the criminal personality central and important from problems one as is determined . Him study , mainly, the same that's it in the name private criminological theory as well as object different kind of crimes, including adult those who did not of crimes subjective determinants has been another many private theories within done is increased. For example, traditional way criminology in textbooks separately separate indicated " Adult not enough between offense (and his prevention get)" subject , of course , adult those who did not of the person criminological description the issue own into takes. Ours in our work of the criminal personality criminal threat source as seeing will be released , although , of course , it is relevant in the situation of the criminal himself criminal to the threat subject to to be or to the victim rotation possible (for example , in lynching). That's why for we the person to crime against safety of the object main element as his *criminogenicity* and *sacrifice point of view in terms of let's look*.

Criminal threat under adult not enough of the person which features the most weaken or on the contrary, his spiritual and legal stability strengthening possible to know the same important. Such ability everyone people for one different to be possible not. But a lot people their own internal characteristics, character and in his actions to each other very similar being them this category to people relatively applied certain criminological tools using learning can.

This tools of the collection basis as modeling method we can Model, you As you know, we are learning of object (adult did not of the person person) to himself special representative as created and is used . An example without a doubt models to the line in criminology , though not included work developed criminal personality model we bring possible". Of the criminal personality "- this criminological of modeling is a product, i.e simplified scheme, criminological of knowledge repetitive elements model , object , its separately elements about known structures in the form of increase through subject knowledge get method own into takes.

In this complex and conflicting criminogenic-criminal situation, there are also children who are actively introduced to one or another religious belief and culture, involved in ethnic conflicts arising from religious reasons. the rational and educational model of learning as the main object of criminal security includes considering him as a rational person who has free will, knows his rights and obligations, and measures them with the rights and obligations of other persons. The main driver of human behavior is his mind, free will, but under certain conditions (unfairly organized society, imperfect laws, allows to be rich and makes others beggars, etc.) as a result, he perceives himself as a mentally retarded person, easily gets involved in criminal activities, and is sometimes forced to commit crimes on his own initiative. In criminology, this phenomenon is called "forced crime".

It can be shown that a teenager cannot develop the reflex of fear of punishment due to congenital brain damage or defects in upbringing. life, especially related to normal sexual development, sexual education and upbringing, as well as possible features: egocentrism, aggression, inability to adapt, impulsiveness , stubbornness, distrust, indifference to the opinions and experiences of others. Addiction to alcohol, drugs, and computer games plays a particularly negative role in having a devastating effect on physiological and psychological areas . As a result of such hobbies, minors develop a psychological dependence on these dangerous activities, a direct dependence on them. Various directions are being developed using non-traditional approaches to explaining crime and its causes. One such approach is based on information theory. In particular, from the criminological point of view, the process of the birth of new information in the human mind is considered as a reaction to something heard or seen, the influence of such reactive information on the actions of a person.

The criminal-legal model of a minor includes the subject's free will or freedom of choice. As a result of an arbitrary decision, a minor commits an act (act, inaction), the negative consequences of which are primarily aimed at him. This means that a minor can create conditions for the commission of a crime against himself or directly initiate a criminal offense against himself, or he can become a criminal himself due to dishonesty, ignorance of the law, etc. It allows to analyze pre-crime and criminal situations in which a minor is a victim. Since the purpose of the protective action is to ensure the normal state of the object, it is necessary to determine which elements of it should be affected. It is through a differentiated impact on these elements that a holistic result can be achieved - internal and external protection of a minor from criminal threats.

Therefore, it is not enough for the subject of management (prevention of crimes) to have the understanding that criminological security in relation to a minor is the reliability of the criminological security system to protect him from the threat of criminal influence. the ability

of a minor to protect himself from this, including the reliability of his environment, as well as the presence of specially created conditions for this. It is important to know which elements determine the direction and level of work of a large number of socio-psychological, moral-legal and other mechanisms that form security relations against crime.

The identity of a minor is the main element or subsystem of criminological security, it deserves the greatest attention in our research. Therefore, first of all, we determine the identity of a minor by criminological, that is, the goals and objectives, structure of criminological security. As mentioned above, this structure makes it possible to distinguish the most important internal and external characteristics and relationships of a person. The structure of a person's worldview can be implemented in different ways, that is, depending on the goals and tasks set by the researcher. As an initial model legal mind and of character consists of the most simple structure designation can Legal consciousness, as a rule, is considered through its ideological and psychological aspects as the most complex components of a person. The main element that we identify is the ideological component of a minor (leading subsystem) with specific characteristics: integrity, purposefulness, self-organization, adaptation to environmental changes, etc. As a second component, following psychologists, we determine mental characteristics.

General, extremely dynamic interdependence of personal components is expressed in the character of a minor, as well as an adult. Despite the various changes that occur during the interaction of a person with the environment, especially in extreme conditions (criminogenic, pre-criminal, criminal, post-criminal), the character in normal conditions almost does not change. Thus, minors, due to the above and other age characteristics, weak psychological and physiological mechanisms of perception, more than adults, may not adequately respond to some events that they observe or study. From here, decisions are made, actions are taken that provoke criminal attacks against themselves or encourage their criminal motives, as a result of which the system of internal protection of a person against a criminal threat is destroyed. According to AS Ovchinsky and SO Chebotarev, who wrote " In the formation of a person as a person", from the period of pregnancy, especially in the first years of infancy, the environment, living conditions, communication, education and upbringing are formed in his mind. reactive information formed in the secret plays a decisive role ". This judgment confirms the need to take into account the environment, with which it is closely related, as an object of criminalistic security of a minor.

According to NN Chernov, "issues of assessing the security system from the point of view of personal psychology have begun to attract the attention of researchers and are the cause of serious discussions due to their underdevelopment, but the formulation of this problem is still relevant today." The environment of a minor as an external element of the object of security against crime includes the same contradictory essence as the minor himself in criminological assessment. On the one hand, the environment is considered as a threat factor, i.e. has a criminogenic and victimogenic effect on a minor; in the second, it has a positive effect on him, that is, it minimizes his criminogenicity, victimhood; Finally, in the third aspect, this element is considered as an incident of direct action against the criminal threat, more precisely, the source of the threat - persons who can expect criminal aggression against a minor.

Environment negative and positive to criteria according to elementary way structure can. Negative The principle is mostly informal, that is by itself appear was (to interests according to) in groups occurs ; positive - regulatory and legal in the documents reinforced official or there is in order according to organize done Usually , they are between to crime against safety of the object the most important complex elements as family , school class , sports team and others is separated . Of course , both unofficial and official group adult not enough to safety effect to do of the subject to the assumptions uncertain or straight away opposite to be can.

Conclusion: Thus, we have determined the personal characteristics of the object of the anti-crime security system or the internal subsystem of protection against the criminal threat. It is oriented towards the environment and is designed to perform a reactive function in the event of a source of criminal threat under the influence of negative factors. another subsystem of protection operates in the person of people who are able, able or obliged to see the events. We consider it appropriate . In criminology , in contrast to the traditional approach to consider the negative aspects of the person (criminogenicity of the offender, victimization of the victim, criminogenic, victim status), in our study. holistic approach to the study of the personality of a minor. However, this does not exclude the analysis and differential evaluation of the characteristics of the object shown, on the contrary, with their help, the integral characteristics of the object are determined and it becomes possible to give a problematic description of it. This sign is intended to play a key role in defining strategic, tactical tasks and the nature of the protective effect on the criminal security object.

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